

libyt: a Tool for Parallel In Situ Analysis with yt

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ABSTRACT

In the era of exascale computing, storage and analysis of large-scale data have become increasingly more important and difficult. In situ analysis provides a promising solution to this challenge. Here we present `libyt` (<https://github.com/calab-ntu/libyt>), an open source C++ library allowing astrophysical simulations to analyze and visualize data with `yt` or other Python packages in parallel during simulation runtime. We describe the methods for reading adaptive mesh refinement data structure, accessing and handling in-memory cell-centered, face-centered, and particle data with minimal memory overhead, and exchanging data among parallel processes. We provide concrete examples of incorporating `libyt` to a simulation code. Furthermore, we demonstrate its capability with two astrophysical simulations, fuzzy dark matter vortices and core-collapse supernovae, with the code `GAMER`.

Keywords: methods: data analysis — methods: miscellaneous

1. INTRODUCTION

Scientific simulations have grown exponentially in both size and complexity. Softwares like ParaView (Ahrens et al. 2005), MATLAB have been widely used in analyzing and visualizing these output dataset. Light weight tools like `yt` (Turk et al. 2011) has also been developed to suit the needs of quantitative analysis for astrophysical data. Even though we can use these tools to successfully accomplish everyday tasks, we suffer from having to store the full dataset on disk first before doing any further analysis. If these tools can directly access the data inside the running simulation and analyze them arbitrarily, then we can greatly reduce disk usage and increase temporal resolution through storing only related data on disk. This is even more helpful when only a small fraction of data is needed or the dataset itself is humongous. ParaView has provided Catalyst for simulations to do in situ analysis inside ParaView, but it lacks agility and requires users to set up the environment. Thus, we decided to develop `libyt`, a C++

library for `yt`, which does in situ analysis in Python environment by directly calling `yt` functions or other Python packages during simulation runtime.

`libyt` provides another way for users to interact with running simulations and their data. We can now monitor the simulation process, and we can run Python script and call Python module to process the in-memory data like how we normally use Python for our every day tasks. This includes extracting a subset from the full dataset, analyzing a time series of data with high temporal resolution, just to name a few. Using `libyt` does not add a time penalty to the analysis, because using Python for in situ analysis and post-processing are exactly the same except the former one reads data from memory and the later one reads data from disks.

`libyt` originates from `Enzo` (Bryan et al. 2014). `Enzo` is a community-developed adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) simulation code, designed for rich, multi-physics hydrodynamic astrophysical calculations. `Enzo` supports in situ analysis with `yt`, but this feature is hard-coded inside it and hasn't yet singled out from `Enzo`. Also, it only supports limited `yt` functions. We extract this embedded Python feature out of `Enzo` into `libyt`, then greatly extend its functionality. This C++ library

Figure 1. Overall structure of `libyt`. It provides an interface for exchanging data between simulations and python instances, thereby enabling in situ parallel analysis using multiple MPI processes. `libyt` can run arbitrary Python scripts and Python modules, though here we focus on `yt`.

can now be applied to other simulation codes and supports most of `yt` functions.

`libyt` is primarily written in Python and C++. It connects simulations to Python, so that we can use Python to analyze data stored in memory during simulation runtime. This does not affect simulation itself, because `libyt` only tells Python how to interpret those block of memory and will not change it. We use Python C application programming interface (API) and NumPy C API (Harris et al. 2020) to achieve this.

In this paper, we will start by describing the code method and how `libyt` is built at Section 2. We then walk through the procedure of implementing `libyt` into simulations at Section 3. We demonstrate some production runs with the GPU-accelerated AMR code `GAMER` (Schive et al. 2018, <https://github.com/gamer-project/gamer>) using `libyt` and show that it plays an important role in large simulations at Section 4. We discuss `libyt` performance, limitations and future directions in Section 5 and conclude in Section 6.

2. CODE METHOD

This section describes how we use embedded Python to build `libyt`, a C++ library for simulation codes to interact with Python. We provide an overview of `libyt` in Section 2.1 and a brief introduction of how `libyt` utilizes the Python C API and NumPy C API in Section 2.2. We describe how `libyt` interacts with `yt` and list the supported `yt` functions in Section 2.3. Section 2.4 discusses the parallelism of `libyt`. Sections 2.5 — 2.8 illustrate respectively how `libyt` collects grid hierarchy, loads intrinsic field data, computes derived field data, and supports particle data.

2.1. Overview of `libyt`

`libyt` provides a bridge that connects simulations to Python instances. Fig. 1 illustrates its overall structure. Simulations can use `libyt` API to call and run

Python scripts during simulation runtime, and Python instances can use `libyt` Python module to request data directly from simulations. Using `libyt` for in situ analysis is very similar to running Python scripts in post-processing (Section 3.8 gives an example), except that data are stored in memory instead of hard drives. `libyt` is general-purpose and can launch arbitrary Python scripts and Python modules, though in this paper we focus on using `yt` for in situ analysis.

When conducting large simulations in parallel using the Message Passing Interface (MPI), simulation data are distributed in multiple processes. It is thus crucial for `libyt` to support MPI as well. When launching N MPI processes, each process will create and launch a `libyt` Python module and Python interpreter. `libyt` handles data I/O between simulations and Python instances, including collecting data from simulations and exchanging data between different MPI processes. The latter is essential for the N Python instances to conduct in situ analysis in parallel since the data required by a Python instance may reside in multiple processes. See Section 2.4 for details.

2.2. Embedding Python in C++ Applications

One can extend the functionality of Python by calling C/C++ functions, and, likewise, one can embed Python in a C/C++ application to enhance its capability. Python provides C API for users to initialize the Python interpreter, create and access Python objects, and run Python codes in a main C/C++ program. Similarly, NumPy provides C API for users to create NumPy array objects so that arrays created in a C/C++ application can be used by the Python interpreter. This includes creating a NumPy array wrapper around an existing C/C++ array or allocating a new NumPy array from scratch and then assigning data.

When initializing `libyt`, it builds a Python module to connect Python to a simulation code and initializes the Python interpreter. This Python module (i) stores simulation information in Python dictionary objects and (ii) provides Python C-extension methods for Python to request data from simulations, as listed below.

- Python dictionary objects
 - `grid.data`: Intrinsic field data, such as gas mass density and gravitational potential.
 - `hierarchy`: AMR grid hierarchy, such as refinement level, grid indices, parent grid indices, grid dimension, and grid coordinates.
 - `param.yt`: Built-in `yt` and `libyt` parameters, such as simulation time, domain dimensionality, code units, and number of grids.

- `param_user`: Frontend-specific parameters, such as equation of state parameters.
- Python C-extension methods
 - `derived_func`: Get derived field data from the local MPI process.
 - `get_field_remote` Get intrinsic or derived field data from remote MPI processes.
 - `get_attr`: Get particle data from the local MPI process.
 - `get_attr_remote` Get particle data from remote MPI processes.

We will describe how to fill in these dictionary objects in the following subsections and provide concrete demonstrations in Section 3.

After creating `libyt` Python module, `libyt` will load the entire user Python script just once at the initialization stage. The Python interpreter then holds the functions and variables defined in this script throughout the entire simulation. This script can define multiple functions so that we can use `libyt` API to call different functions when performing in situ analysis at different simulation stages. Operations and variables only needed to be initialized once should be put outside of a function to prevent from multiple initializations. These functions support loading arguments from simulation codes, which is important for flexibility. See Section 3.8 for some explicit examples.

The essence of `libyt` is to analyze the in-memory simulation data without storing them on disk. We can categorize these data into two kinds: *intrinsic* data that can be passed to Python directly and *derived* data that require further manipulation by a simulation code before passing to Python. For intrinsic data, typical examples in a hydrodynamic code include gas mass density and gravitational potential. We use NumPy C API `PyArray_SimpleNewFromData` to wrap around existing C arrays, allowing Python to access data directly without additional memory allocation. See Section 2.6 for details and Section 3.3 for a demonstration. For derived data, examples include converting the face-centered magnetic field to cell-centered and computing various thermodynamic variables for a given equation of state. We allocate arrays, wrap them using NumPy C API, and then pass the ownership to Python¹. It is Python’s responsibility to free these arrays when the reference count drops to zero. See Section 2.7 for details and Section 3.4 for a demonstration.

¹ We use `PyArray_ENABLEFLAGS` with the flag `NPY_ARRAY_OWNDATA`.

Table 1. Supported key `yt` functions.

Functions	Limitations
Derived quantity	
Projection plot	
Slice plot	
Extract uniform grids	
1D/2D profile	
Line plot	
Annotations	Some functions require all MPI processes to call <code>save</code> when saving a figure.
Volume rendering	Number of MPI processes must be even.
Particle data	
Data objects	

NOTE—Generally speaking, `libyt` supports every `yt` function that involves all MPI processes in data I/O. See Section 5.3 for details.

`libyt` supports particles, which can have different types and attributes. The particle attributes can also be categorized into intrinsic attributes (e.g., position and velocity) and derived attributes (e.g., momentum and energy). See Sections 2.8 and 3.5.

2.3. Connecting `libyt` to `yt`

We create a new `yt` frontend for `libyt`, hereafter referred to as `libyt` frontend². It is very similar to how other simulation codes communicate with `yt` in post-processing, except that the `io` module in `libyt` frontend deals with in-memory data transfer instead of hard disk I/O.

`libyt` can access the field information of `yt` predefined fields. Moreover, when applying `libyt` to a simulation code already with a `yt` frontend for post-processing, it can inherit the field information from this `yt` frontend. It allows `libyt` to reuse post-processing scripts with minimum modifications (see Section 3.8), which greatly improves its capability and flexibility.

Table 1 lists the key `yt` functions supported by `libyt`. Generally speaking, `libyt` supports all functions of `yt` unless there is asymmetric data I/O in different MPI processes. We elaborate on this minor limitation in Section 5.3.

2.4. Parallelism

² <https://github.com/cindytsai/yt/tree/libyt>. It will be merged into the official repository of `yt` soon.

`yt` supports MPI parallelism and it is desirable for `libyt` to utilize it directly. There is however one important caveat. For post-processing, the grid and particle data stored on hard disks are accessible by all MPI processes, similar to a shared-memory mechanism. `yt` can thus distribute data and associated computation to different MPI processes quite arbitrarily without extra MPI communication. But the way `yt` distributes these data is, in general, different from the distribution of in-memory data during simulation runtime. In other words, there is no guarantee that the data requested by `yt` for each MPI process already locate in the same process when conducting in situ analysis. To solve this problem, `libyt` performs additional MPI communication when necessary to redistribute the grid and particle data in accordance with `yt`.

Many common MPI routines need handshaking between a sender and a receiver. However, since `libyt` cannot know in advance what kind of communication pattern a Python script needs, it is difficult to schedule point-to-point communications that fit any kind of algorithms and any number of MPI processes. To solve this problem, `libyt` use one-sided communication in MPI, also known as Remote Memory Access (RMA), by which one no longer needs to explicitly specify senders and receivers. By creating a RMA “epoch”, for which all MPI process will enter, each process can access the data in other processes without requiring explicit participation of remote processes.

One catch is that the RMA synchronization routine `MPI.Win_fence`, which starts and ends an epoch, is a collective operation requiring all processes to participate. It means that all MPI processes must enter the `yt` data I/O stage together. If, however, some `yt` analysis routines only involve a subset of MPI processes in the data I/O stage, the RMA operation will hang and fail. We will discuss this limitation further in Section 5.3

Before transferring data, we first collect grid indices requested by `yt` in every MPI process so that each process knows what data to prepare for others. The data I/O module in `libyt` frontend then calls the Python C-extension method `get_field_remote` (for field data) or `get_attr_remote` (for particle data) to trigger the data exchange process. The whole process of this one-sided communication can be summarized as follows.

1. Create a MPI window that allows memory to be dynamically exposed and un-exposed.
2. Prepare data and attach a data buffer to MPI window. Then get the address of the attached buffer.
3. Gather the data buffer information such as address, sizes, and data type in each MPI process.

4. Open the RMA epoch to start the data transfer process.
5. Fetch data from remote processes.
6. Close the RMA epoch to end the data transfer process.
7. Free the data buffer.
8. Return the data array one by one back to Python C-extension method.
9. Close the MPI window.

In large simulations, the data communication size may exceed the maximum number of data elements allowed to be transferred at a time³. To overcome this limitation, `libyt` splits the data transfer of large arrays into multiple MPI calls automatically to ensure that each transfer does not exceed the upper limit.

2.5. Collecting Grid Information

In AMR simulations, the computational domain consists of grids with different sizes and resolutions. `libyt` helps collect the information of this grid hierarchy, such as the coordinates, dimension, indices, resolution, and number of particles of each grid, and then passes this information to `yt`. See Section 3.6 for a demonstration.

Not all AMR simulation codes store the full grid hierarchy redundantly in each MPI process. For example, `GAMER` (Schive et al. 2018) only stores the information of local grid hierarchy associated with each MPI process. In this case, `libyt` can also help collect the hierarchy information from all MPI processes such that each process only needs to prepare the local grid hierarchy held by itself. After gathering the full grid hierarchy, the information is broadcasted to all MPI processes and then stored in the `libyt` Python dictionary object `hierarchy` (see Section 2.2) so that the `yt` module in each process can access it through `libyt` frontend.

2.6. Loading Intrinsic Fields

Intrinsic fields refer to the data stored in memory during simulation runtime, for example, gas mass density and gravitational potential in a gravitational hydrodynamic simulation. To directly utilize these data in Python without altering them, we use NumPy API to create a wrapper around each field data array. This wrapper allows Python to read a simulation data array directly without allocating extra memory. We then

³ The upper limit is 2^{31} since the MPI parameter `count` uses the 32-bit integer data type.

organize all field data under `libyt` Python dictionary object `grid_data` (see Section 2.2). After finishing in situ analysis, these data will not be modified or freed so that the simulation can continue without any change.

Some simulation codes allocate ghost cells for each grid permanently (e.g., `Enzo`) while some codes do not (e.g., `GAMER`). For the former, `libyt` can wrap the entire array including ghost cells and read only the target region. This process does not require additional memory allocation either.

2.7. Computing Derived Fields

Derived fields refer to new field data derived from intrinsic fields. In other words, they are not stored in memory during simulation runtime and require additional manipulation on intrinsic fields to generate the data. For example, the constrained transport algorithm in magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) uses staggered grids to store the *face-centered* magnetic field (e.g., Stone et al. 2008). However, it is usually more convenient for analysis to convert the field to cell-centered to be consistent with other hydrodynamic variables. Here the original face-centered magnetic field is an intrinsic field and the corresponding cell-centered magnetic field is a derived field. Another example is the conversion between various cell-centered hydrodynamic and thermodynamic variables. This conversion can be either straightforward, such as computing velocity from momentum and mass density, or complicated, such as computing temperature from gas mass density, internal energy, and electron fraction for a core-collapse supernova equation of state (e.g., Steiner et al. 2013) that requires table look-up.

Unlike intrinsic fields, computing derived fields require allocating extra memory, which can be memory-consuming if we compute them on all grids at once. To alleviate this potential issue, `libyt` only prepares the data requested by `yt`. For example, operations like slice plots only needs a small portion of grid data where the slice cuts through. Furthermore, `libyt` takes advantage of the data chunking mechanism in `yt`. Before actually reading data from disk or memory, `yt` identifies what data it needs, groups these data into chunks, and then reads and computes these data chunks one at a time. So `libyt` does not have to prepare all the required data for a given analysis at once.

For converting face-centered data to cell-centered, simulation codes do not need to provide any additional routine for this conversion. `libyt` frontend can do it automatically through the following steps.

1. Read the entire data array with or without ghost cells from the Python dictionary object `grid_data`.

2. Get the target subarray through NumPy indexing, excluding ghost cells.
3. Convert data to cell-centered by taking average over neighboring data along the direction normal to the target face.

For computing a general derived field, a simulation code must first provide a data-generating C function defining this new field and pass it to `libyt`. See Section 3.4 for a demonstration. After that, the `io` module in `libyt` frontend can call Python C-extension method `derived_func` to compute this derived field in the following steps.

1. Allocate a data array to store derived fields.
2. Invoke `derived_func` to compute and store the derived field data in the data array.
3. Use NumPy API to wrap around this data array and return to Python.

2.8. Supporting Particle Data

One key difference between particle and grid data is that particle data may not be contiguous in memory, so one cannot use the NumPy array wrapper directly. In addition, there can be multiple particle types, each with different attributes. For example, “star” particles can have metallicity, “black hole” particles can have spins, and “dark matter” particles can have softening length.

`libyt` allocates a data array and then gathers particle data through a user-provided C function (see Section 3.5 for a demonstration). This function can also generate derived particle attributes. To reduce memory overhead, `libyt` only prepares the particle data on the grids specified by `yt`. It is similar to the procedure of computing derived fields as described in the previous subsection. The `io` module in `libyt` frontend calls Python C-extension methods `get_attr` and `get_attr_remote` to prepare particle data in the following steps.

1. Allocate a particle data array.
2. Invoke `get_attr` and `get_attr_remote` to write particle data to this array.
3. Use NumPy API to wrap around this data array and return to Python.

3. DEMONSTRATION

In this section, we provide code snippets in C++ to demonstrate how to implement `libyt` into a simulation code. Fig. 2 shows the procedure of using `libyt` for in situ analysis during simulation runtime. Table 2 lists all the corresponding functions provided by the `libyt` API.

Figure 2. Procedure of performing in situ analysis with `libyt`. Note that the simulation parameters (e.g., current time), grid distribution (e.g., with AMR), and particles associated with each grid can change during simulation runtime so they are reset during each iteration of the simulation.

Table 2. `libyt` API.

API	Usage	Section
<code>yt_init</code>	Initialize <code>libyt</code> .	Section 3.1
<code>yt_set_parameter</code>	Set <code>yt</code> parameters.	Section 3.2
<code>yt_add_user_parameter_*</code>	Set code-specific parameters.	Section 3.2
<code>yt_get_fieldsPtr</code>	Fill in field information.	Section 3.3
<code>yt_getGridInfo_Dimensions</code>	Get grid dimensions in derived field functions.	Section 3.4
<code>yt_getGridInfo_FieldData</code>	Get field data in derived field functions.	Section 3.4
<code>yt_get_particlesPtr</code>	Fill in particle information.	Section 3.5
<code>yt_get_gridsPtr</code>	Fill in grid information and data.	Section 3.6
<code>yt_commit_grids</code>	Commit settings before performing in situ analysis.	Section 3.7
<code>yt_inline</code>	Call a Python function without arguments.	Section 3.8
<code>yt_inline_argument</code>	Call a Python function with arguments.	Section 3.8
<code>yt_free_gridsPtr</code>	Free the resources allocated by <code>libyt</code> .	Section 3.9
<code>yt_finalize</code>	Finalize <code>libyt</code> .	Section 3.10

3.1. Initialization

At the initialization stage, we set the general configuration of `libyt` such as the logging level and debugging mode, and loads a user-provided Python script for performing in situ analysis later. The debugging mode checks, for example, whether field information, particle information, and AMR grid hierarchy are set correctly. We also initialize Python interpreter and `libyt` Python module at this stage, which only needs to be done once.

The following example loads the Python script `inline_script.py`, disables both logging and debugging, and initializes `libyt` by calling the API function `yt_init`.

```
yt_param_libyt param_libyt;
param_libyt.script = "inline_script";
param_libyt.verbose = YT_VERBOSE_OFF;
param_libyt.check_data = false;
yt_init( argc, argv, &param_libyt );
```

3.2. Setting Parameters

In the following example, we store all `yt`-specific parameters in `param_yt` and pass it to `yt` by calling the API function `yt_set_parameter`. These parameters include, for instance, `frontend` (name of the corresponding `yt` frontend), `current_time` (current simulation time), `time_unit` (time unit in seconds), `dimensionality` (domain dimensionality 1/2/3), `num_fields` (number of fields), `num_species` (number of particle types), `num_attr` (number of particle attributes associated with each type), and `num_grids_local` (number of local grids on this MPI process). Note that we use `GAMER` as an example, which already has a corresponding `yt` frontend. Hence we can directly borrow the field information defined in this frontend without the need to redefine it here. (see Section 2.3).

```
yt_param_yt param_yt;
param_yt.frontend = "gamer";
param_yt.current_time = 0.0;
param_yt.time_unit = 3.1557e13;
param_yt.dimensionality = 3;
param_yt.num_fields = 5;
param_yt.num_grids_local = 100;
/* Set particle types. */
yt_species *species_list = new yt_species [1];
species_list[0].species_name = "io";
species_list[0].num_attr = 4;
param_yt.num_species = 1;
param_yt.species_list = species_list;
yt_set_parameter( &param_yt );
```

Simulation codes can also define their own parameters and pass them to `yt` by calling the API function `yt_add_user_parameter_*`, where the asterisk `*` shall be replaced by `int`, `long`, `float`, `double`, or `string` depending on the input data type. The following example adds a single integer parameter `mhd` to the `GAMER` frontend indicative of disabling MHD.

```
const int MHD = 0;
yt_add_user_parameter_int( "mhd", 1, &MHD );
```

3.3. Setting Field Information

To set the field information, such as field name, unit, and data format, a simulation code first calls the API function `yt_get_fieldsPtr` to get a pointer pointing to `yt_field` and then fills in the information of each field. The following example assumes that the first field is gas mass density named `Dens`, which is cell-centered, in the single-precision floating-point data format (`YT_FLOAT`), and contiguous in memory along the x-axis (`swap_axes = true`). Note that `libyt` also supports data continuous along the z-axis by setting `swap_axes = false`. By default, `libyt` assumes no ghost cell.

```
yt_field *fields;
yt_get_fieldsPtr( &fields );
fields[0].field_name = "Dens";
fields[0].field_type = "cell-centered";
fields[0].field_dtype = YT_FLOAT;
fields[0].swap_axes = true;
```

3.4. Adding Derived Fields

We have introduced derived fields in Section 2.7. The procedure of adding a derived field is similar to registering an intrinsic field (Section 3.3) except that a simulation code must provide a data-generating function to

construct each derived field. The following example creates a derived field “Half_Dens”, which simply divides the original density field by 2, by setting `field_type` to `derived_func` and providing a data-generating function `half_dens`. Other parameters are the same as setting intrinsic fields.

```
void half_dens(int len, long *gids, char
*field, yt_array *data);
...
fields[0].field_name = "Half_Dens";
fields[0].field_type = "derived_func";
fields[0].derived_func = half_dens;
fields[0].field_dtype = YT_FLOAT;
fields[0].swap_axes = true;
```

The function prototype of a data-generating function, such as `half_dens`, is also given in the above example. Here `gids` lists the target grid indices, `len` is the length of the list, `field` is the field name, and `yt_data *data` is for storing the output derived field data excluding ghost cells.

3.5. Setting Particle Information

Setting particle information is similar to adding a derived field. A simulation code first calls the API function `yt_get_particlesPtr` to get a pointer pointing to `yt_particle` and then fills in the information of each particle type. For flexibility, different particle types can have different attributes, and each attribute can have its own data format (e.g., single-precision floating-point `YT_FLOAT`, double-precision floating-point `YT_DOUBLE`, integer `YT_INT`). For each particle type, a simulation code must provide a data-generating C function to return the associated particle attribute data.

The following example assumes only one particle type “io” (set in Section 3.2) with four attributes “ParPosX”, “ParPosY”, “ParPosZ”, and “ParMass” stored in the single-precision floating-point data format. `par_io_get_attr` is the corresponding data-generating function for all attributes associated with this particle type, which is passed to `libyt` via the function pointer `get_attr`. Note that the particle position attributes are requisite for all particle types, which can be specified by the parameters `coor_x`, `coor_y`, `coor_z`.

```
void par_io_get_attr(int len, long *gids, char
*attr, yt_array *data);
...
yt_particle *particles;
yt_get_particlesPtr( &particles );
char *attr_name[] = {"ParPosX", "ParPosY",
"ParPosZ", "ParMass"};
for(int v=0; v<4; v++){
    particles[0].attr_list[v].attr_name =
attr_name[v];
    particles[0].attr_list[v].attr_dtype =
YT_FLOAT;
}
particles[0].coor_x = attr_name[0];
particles[0].coor_y = attr_name[1];
particles[0].coor_z = attr_name[2];
particles[0].get_attr = par_io_get_attr;
```

The function prototype of a particle attribute data-generating function, such as `par_io_get_attr`, is also given in the above example, where `len`, `gids`, `data` are the same as the data-generating function for a derived field (Section 3.4) and `attr` specifies the target particle attribute. This function should collect the attribute data of the specific grid indices listed in `gids` and store the data in `data`. Note that we can also create *derived* particle attributes using this data-generating function.

3.6. Setting Local Grids Information

As described in Section 2.5, each MPI process only needs to provide the hierarchy information and data of local grids associated with this process. The following example first calls the API function `yt_get_gridsPtr` to get a pointer pointing to `yt_grids` and then fills in the information of the first grid `grids[0]` as a demonstration. `libyt` uses 0-indexed so both the grid index `id` and AMR level `level` start from 0. The parent grid index `parent_id` is set to `-1` since this grid is at the root level and does not have a parent grid. The field data pointer `data` points to the in-memory data array of the first field on this grid. Note that the field data pointers set here and the field information array set in Section 3.3 must have the same order. We also set the grid’s left edge, right edge, and number of cells along each spatial direction.

```

yt_grid *grids;
yt_get_gridsPtr( &grids );
grids[0].id = 0;
grids[0].parent_id = -1;
grids[0].level = 0;
grids[0].field_data[0].data_ptr = data;
for(int d=0; d<3; d++){
    grids[0].left_edge[d] = 0.0;
    grids[0].right_edge[d] = 1.0;
    grids[0].grid_dimensions[d] = 8;
}

```

3.7. Committing Settings

After setting aforementioned prerequisite information, a simulation code must call the API function `yt_commit_grids` before performing in situ analysis. This function will pass all information to `libyt` Python module.

```
yt_commit_grids();
```

3.8. Performing In Situ Analysis

A simulation code can call all the Python functions defined in the Python script loaded at the initialization stage (i.e., "inline_script" in Section 3.1). We use the API function `yt_inline_argument` to execute Python functions with arguments or `yt_inline` otherwise. The following example illustrates the usage of both cases, where `func1()` has no argument and `func2("str_arg")` has a single string variable "str_arg".

```

yt_inline("func1");
yt_inline_argument("func2", 1, "\"str_arg\"");

```

A python script for in situ analysis is *very similar* to that for post-processing, which allows `libyt` to reuse a post-processing script with minimum modifications and thereby greatly lowers the barrier of conducting in situ analysis. The only differences are that a `libyt` script loads data using `yt.frontends.libyt.libytDataset()` and must enable the parallelism feature in `yt` by calling `yt.enable_parallelism()`. The following example shows a post-processing script that creates a projection plot from the density field of the file `Data000000` and stores the figure on disk on the root MPI process.

```

import yt
yt.enable_parallelism()
def func():
    ds = yt.load("Data000000")
    proj = yt.ProjectionPlot(ds, "density")
    if yt.is_root():
        proj.save()

```

In comparison, below is the corresponding in situ analysis script, which simply replaces `ds=yt.load("Data000000")` in the post-processing script with `ds=yt.frontends.libyt.libytDataset()`.

```

import yt
yt.enable_parallelism()
def func():
    ds = yt.frontends.libyt.libytDataset()
    proj = yt.ProjectionPlot(ds, "density")
    if yt.is_root():
        proj.save()

```

We use the term "libyt fields" for fields listed in the field information array described in Section 3.3, which can be either intrinsic or derived fields. The term "yt fields" refer to fields either defined in the field information class `field.py` in a `yt` frontend or `yt` built-in fields. `libyt` supports both of them. To distinguish between `libyt` fields and `yt` fields, we mark `libyt` fields with the frontend name set in Section 3.2. In the example below, the first line uses the `libyt` field ("gamer", "Dens"), where `gamer` marks the frontend name, and the second line uses the `yt` field `velocity_x` defined in the `GAMER` `yt` frontend.

```

yt.SlicePlot(ds, "z", ("gamer", "Dens"))
yt.SlicePlot(ds, "z", "velocity_x")

```

3.9. Freeing Resources

After finishing in situ analysis in a single iteration of the simulation, a simulation code should release the resources temporarily allocated by `libyt` via the API function `yt_free_gridsPtr`.

```
yt_free_gridsPtr();
```

3.10. Finalization

When terminating the whole simulation process, a simulation code can clean up the Python interpreter by calling the API function `yt_finalize`, which must be done before calling `MPI_Finalize`.

```
yt_finalize();
```

4. APPLICATIONS

To demonstrate the importance of in situ analysis and the capability of `libyt`, we have implemented `libyt` into `GAMER` and applied it to two astrophysical applications, namely, fuzzy dark matter vortices (Section 4.1) and core-collapse supernovae (Section 4.2).

4.1. Fuzzy Dark Matter Vortices

Fuzzy dark matter (FDM) is a promising dark matter candidate consisting of ultralight bosons with a particle mass of $\sim 10^{-22} - 10^{-20}$ eV (Hu et al. 2000; Schive et al. 2014a; Marsh 2016). Because of the large de Broglie wavelength compared to the mean interparticle separation, FDM is best described by a classical scalar field governed by the Schrödinger-Poisson equation. FDM halos feature a central compact solitonic core surrounded by fluctuating density granules resulting from wave function interference. Quantum vortices can form in density voids caused by fully destructive interference (Chiueh 1998; Hui et al. 2021). The dynamics and topology of these vortices in a realistic FDM halo have not been investigated thoroughly with three-dimensional simulations, largely due to the very high spatial and temporal resolution required. In situ analysis with `libyt` thus provides a promising approach for this study.

We use `GAMER` to simulate the evolution of an FDM halo. The simulations have been performed on the Taiwan 3 supercomputer at the National Center for High-performance Computing in Taiwan, where each computing node has two Intel Xeon Platinum 8280 28-Core CPUs. We use 560 CPU cores by launching 20 MPI processes and 28 OpenMP threads per MPI process. The FDM halo has a virial mass $M_h = 7.0 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$ and a virial radius 110 kpc. The half-density radius of the central soliton is 280 pc (Schive et al. 2014b). The density granules have a characteristic length scale similar to the soliton radius. The simulation box size is 250 kpc, covered by a 640^3 base-level grid with six refinement levels. The first three refinement levels, achieving a modest resolution of 49 pc, are for resolving density granules of the entire halo. The last three refinement levels, achieving a maximum resolution of 6.2 pc, are necessary for resolving the fine structure and dynamical evolution of vortices within a distance 3.2 kpc from the central soliton.

The characteristic timescale of density granules, proportional to $M_h^{-2/3}$, is ~ 10 Myr for this halo. Assuming

FDM vortices and granules share a similar timescale, we thus evolve the system for 11.25 Myr. The evolution time-step on the maximum refinement level imposed by the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy stability condition is 4.0×10^2 yr. To properly capture vortex dynamics, we aim for analyzing vortex properties with a temporal resolution of 3.5×10^{-2} Myr, corresponding to 321 analysis samples within the entire simulation and 88 sub-steps on the maximum refinement level between each sample.

Each simulation snapshot, including density, real part, imaginary part, gravitational potential, and AMR hierarchy, takes 116 GB. Accordingly, the total data size of 321 simulation snapshots required by post-processing is ~ 37 TB, which is quite expensive. However, it is actually unnecessary to dump all these snapshots since our region of interest is only the vortex lines around the halo center. To this end, we use `libyt` to invoke the `yt` function `covering_grid` to extract a uniform-resolution grid centered at the halo center and store these grid data instead of simulation snapshots on disk. The grid dimension is 1024^3 and the spatial resolution is 6.2 pc (i.e., the maximum resolution in the simulation), corresponding to a grid width of 6.3 kpc. By computing and storing the real and imaginary parts of wave function, each grid only consumes 8 GB of disk space (assuming single precision), roughly 15 times smaller than that required by post-processing snapshots.

These uniform-resolution arrays extracted by `libyt` are stored on disk so that they can be further analyzed by post-processing. For example, to identify FDM vortices, we compute the radial density profile and then normalize the density at each cell by the average density at that radius to construct a “flattened” density field. Since FDM vortices form in density voids, they can be identified by taking the reciprocal of this flattened density field and searching for high-value regions. We use ParaView to plot the volume rendering of this reciprocal flattened density field in Fig. 3. Vortex lines and rings are manifest in the entire domain. Fig. 4 further shows a close-up of a vortex reconnection process, where the time interval between adjacent panels is 3.5×10^{-2} Myr. Note that this time interval is the same as the temporal resolution of our in-situ analysis, which highlights the importance of `libyt` for achieving such a high temporal resolution to resolve the very short dynamical timescale associated with vortex reconnection. Moreover, the high spatial resolution is critical for resolving the substructure of individual vortex, such as the whorl-like pattern along each vortex line.

4.2. Core-Collapse Supernova

Figure 3. Volume rendering of quantum vortices in a fuzzy dark matter halo. Vortex lines and rings are manifest in the entire domain. Here we use `libyt` to extract uniform-resolution data from an AMR simulation on-the-fly and then visualize it with ParaView during post-processing. See text for details. Tick labels represent cell indices.

Figure 4. Vortex reconnection process in a fuzzy dark matter halo. Thanks to the in-situ analysis enabled by `libyt`, our analysis can not only achieve a very high temporal resolution (3.5×10^{-2} Myr) to resolve the short dynamical timescale associated with vortex reconnection, but also achieve a very high spatial resolution (6.2 pc) to resolve the substructure of individual vortex, such as the whorl-like pattern along each vortex line.

We use `GAMER` to simulate core-collapse supernova explosions. The simulations have been performed on a local GPU cluster with one AMD Ryzen Threadripper 2950X 16-Core CPU and one NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 SUPER GPU on each computing node. We use 64 CPU cores and 4 GPUs by launching 8 MPI processes, 8 OpenMP threads per MPI process, and having two MPI processes access the same GPU using the CUDA

Multi-Process Service (MPS). The simulations involve a rich set of physics modules, including hydrodynamics, self-gravity, a parameterized light-bulb scheme for neutrino heating and cooling with a fixed neutrino luminosity (Couch 2013), a parameterized deleptonization scheme (Liebendörfer 2005), an effective general relativistic potential (O’Connor & Couch 2018), and a nuclear equation of state (Steiner et al. 2013). For the hy-

Figure 5. Entropy distribution in a core-collapse supernova simulation plotted by `libyt`. Panel (a) shows a thin slice through the central proto-neutron star in the post-bounce phase. The proto-neutron star has a radius of ~ 10 km and the shock stalls at ~ 200 km. Panel (b) shows the underlying AMR grid structure, where each grid consists of 16^3 cells, achieving a maximum resolution of ~ 0.5 km. We perform in situ analysis every 1.5×10^{-2} ms.

hydrodynamics scheme, we adopt the van Leer predictor-corrector integrator (Falle 1991; van Leer 2006), the piecewise parabolic method for spatial data reconstruction (Colella & Woodward 1984), and the HLLC Riemann solver (Toro 2009). The simulation box size is 2×10^4 km. The base-level grid dimension is 160^3 and there are eight refinement levels, reaching a maximum spatial resolution of ~ 0.5 km.

`libyt` facilitates closely monitoring the simulation progress during runtime, such as the grid refinement

Figure 6. Radial density profile of the proto-neutron star in a core-collapse supernova simulation plotted by `libyt`.

distribution, the status and location of shock wave (e.g., stalling, revival, breakout), and the evolution of the central proto-neutron star. We perform in situ analysis every 1.5×10^{-2} ms. In Fig. 5, we use the `yt` function `SlicePlot` to show the gas entropy distribution on a slice through the box center in the post-bounce phase. It demonstrates the derived field functionality (see Section 2.7) by calling the nuclear equation of state to get entropy. The shock stalls at ~ 200 km during this stage; whether shock revival can occur in a later epoch depends on various conditions such as the neutrino luminosity. A proto-neutron star forms at the center with a radius of ~ 10 km. Turbulent flow is manifest in the post-shock region. Fig. 6 shows the radial density profile of the central proto-neutron star, generated by the `yt` function `ProfilePlot`. Note that both the slice and profile data can be save on disk with the `yt` function `save_as_dataset` for remaking figures in post-processing.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Open Source Software

`libyt` is free and open source, which does not depend on any non-free or non-open source software. The code is maintained on GitHub. We use GitHub Action to automate tests for new pushes and pull requests. These tests check if `libyt` can build successfully on a Linux system and also verify if the code can run in both serial and parallel modes. Table 3 lists the important online resources of `libyt`.

Table 3. A list of resources for `libyt`.

Source	Link
Source code	https://github.com/calab-ntu/libyt
Documentation	https://github.com/calab-ntu/libyt#libyt
Slack channel	https://yt-project.slack.com/channels/libyt
Mailing list	libyt-users@googlegroups.com

Figure 7. Strong scaling of `libyt`. We compare the performance between in situ analysis with `libyt` and post-processing for computing 2D profiles on a `GAMER` dataset with seven AMR levels and a total of 9.9×10^8 cells. `libyt` outperforms post-processing by $\sim 10 - 30\%$ since the former does not require loading data from disk. The dotted line shows the ideal scaling for reference. `libyt` and post-processing show a similar deviation from the ideal scaling when increasing the number of processes. It is expected since `libyt` directly utilizes the MPI parallelism of `yt` so the scaling bottleneck lies in `yt`.

5.2. Performance

Fig. 7 shows the strong scaling of `libyt`, where we measure the performance with an increasing number of processors and a fixed problem size. The results are obtained from computing 2D profiles on a `GAMER` FDM dataset with a 384^3 base-level grid and six refinement levels. There are 3,776 grids, each of which consists of 64^3 cells, corresponding to a total of 9.9×10^8 cells. We compare the performance between in situ analysis with `libyt` and post-processing using the same Python script (except for the line for loading a dataset; see Section 3.8). `libyt` outperforms post-processing by

$\sim 10 - 30\%$ since the former avoids loading data from disk to memory. However, since `libyt` directly utilizes the MPI parallelism of `yt` (see Section 2.4), the scaling bottleneck lies in `yt`. As a result, the parallel efficiencies of `libyt` and post-processing are similar and both deviate from the ideal scaling when increasing the number of processors.

5.3. Limitations

Because `libyt` borrows the parallelism feature of `yt`, its performance and limitations strongly depend on how `yt` decomposes and distributes tasks. Most importantly, `libyt` uses synchronous data I/O (see Section 2.4) so all MPI processes must enter the data I/O stage together. As a result, all processes must run the same `yt` operation in an inline Python script if the operation requires data I/O; otherwise the program will hang and fail.

Some `yt` functions may violate the above condition. For example, for a figure annotated with streamlines using `annotate_streamlines`, `yt` needs to perform additional I/O when calling the `save` method to save this figure. This is straightforward in post-processing since all MPI processes can access data on disk independently and thus only one process need to call `save`. By contrast, for `libyt` all MPI processes must call `save` to avoid hanging due to synchronous data I/O. Several annotation functions, such as `annotate_quiver`, `annotate_cquiver`, `annotate_velocity`, `annotate_line_integral_convolution`, `annotate_magnetic_field`, and `annotate_particles`, also have the same limitation. However, saving the same figure redundantly is not a serious problem as long as it does not corrupt an output file since this operation is not time-consuming.

Volume rendering in `yt` also has asymmetric data I/O when saving figures. Some MPI processes may not participate I/O when the number of processes is odd. A compromised solution is thus to launch an even number of processes and have all processes call `save`.

The above limitations are mainly caused by the synchronous data I/O mechanism currently implemented in `libyt`. They can be fixed by either switching to asynchronous I/O in `libyt` or by revising the way `yt` decomposes and distributes tasks. We will address these limitations in the future.

5.4. Future Directions

5.4.1. Fortran

Some AMR codes are written in Fortran, for example, `FLASH` (Fryxell et al. 2000) and `RAMSES` (Teyssier 2002). However, `libyt` currently only supports C/C++ appli-

cations. Future versions of `libyt` will include a Fortran API for all the functions listed in Table 2.

5.4.2. Particle-Based Codes

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5.4.3. Dask

Dask (Rocklin 2015) is a flexible library for parallel computing in Python with growing popularity in the Python ecosystem. By encoding parallel computations into task graphs and executing jobs dynamically using a task scheduler, Dask can handle load balancing and task dependencies efficiently and resiliently. Since `libyt` performs in situ analysis in Python, it is possible and desirable to support Dask, which can also potentially solve the limitations described in Section 5.3.

To support Dask in `libyt`, we need to assign one MPI process as scheduler, one process as client, and the rest as workers. The client is responsible for generating task graphs, informing the scheduler about what to compute, and aggregating results from workers. The scheduler is the middle layer between the client and workers. It instructs workers to execute the jobs requested by the client. The initialization and linking of scheduler, client, and workers can be wrapped and performed by `libyt`. This is very different from the current structure of `libyt`, where each process initializes a Python interpreter and all processes work together on the same level using MPI.

We can improve the data exchange process of `libyt` by Dask. By specifying what data each MPI process should get, asking workers to prepare local grid and particle data, and encoding the data exchange among workers into a Dask graph, it is possible to exchange data with more flexibility and in an asynchronous way. Since data I/O is performed by workers, simulation processes should only run on those worker nodes, and thus we need to launch two extra MPI processes: one for the Dask scheduler and one for the Dask client.

5.4.4. ParaView

ParaView is an open-source, multi-platform data analysis and visualization tool used in many fields. It is designed to analyze large datasets using distributed-memory computing resources. It also provides an in situ analysis interface Catalyst⁴, allowing simulations to perform analysis, output data, and visualize results with ParaView on-the-fly. The relation between Catalyst and ParaView is similar to that between `libyt` and `yt`.

To use Catalyst, typically developers need to write an adaptor to either describe the simulation data structure or even convert the data structure to a format recognizable by Catalyst. `libyt` can potentially serve as the middle layer between Catalyst and simulation codes supporting `libyt`. Since `libyt` already has the simulation information and data, it can become a unified adaptor to directly communicate with Catalyst, which avoids reinventing the wheel. We plan to support this feature in the future.

6. CONCLUSIONS

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We thank to National Center for High-performance Computing (NCHC) for providing computational and storage resources. We also thank Kuo-Chuan Pan and He-Feng Hsieh for implementing the core-collapse supernova simulations into `GAMER`. H. S. acknowledges funding support from the Jade Mountain Young Scholar Award No. NTU-111V1201-5, sponsored by the Ministry of Education, Taiwan. This research is partially supported by the National Science and Technology Council (NSTC) of Taiwan under Grants No. NSTC 111-2628-M-002-005-MY4, No. NSTC 108-2112-M-002-023-MY3 and the NTU Academic Research-Career Development Project under Grant No. NTU-CDP-111L7779.

Software: `yt` (Turk et al. 2011), ParaView (Ahrens et al. 2005), `GAMER` (Schive et al. 2018)

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- ⁴ <https://catalyst-in-situ.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

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